

AWARENESS OF PREGNANCY -RELATED RISKS AMONG RURAL PREGNANT WOMEN OF PARBHANI DISTRICT

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MS Received: 08.03.2025; MS Revised:08.04.2025; MS Accepted:09.04.2025)

MS 3398

(RESEARCH PAPER IN COMMUNITY SCIENCE,)

Abstract

A sample of 150 rural pregnant women belonging to middle and low SES groups residing in 5 villages of Parbhani district were selected by adopting purposive random sampling method. The data pertaining to the study were collected by personally interviewing the sample rural pregnant women based on open ended interview schedule. Irrespective of Socio- economic status, it was observed that a higher percentage of rural pregnant women (87-92 %) were unaware about bad obstetric history like congenital anomalies, early onset of labour, prolonged rupture of membrane, preterm delivery, breech delivery and fetal distress. With respect to the awareness of rural pregnant women about danger signs of pregnancy, even though a higher percentage of them (60-89 %) were aware about some signs like vaginal bleeding/ discharge, weak fetal movements, convulsions and persistent swelling are dangerous in pregnancy, however majority of them (43-87%) were found to be unaware about signs like excessive vomiting, severe headache, visual disturbances, difficulty in breathing and abdominal pain are hazardous signs during this period. Overall, these results indicate that there is a great need to educate pregnant women about obstetric danger signs, which could go a long way in improving the maternal and fetal outcomes.

Keywords: High risk pregnancy, Maternal mortality, Morbidity, Obstetric history, Dangerous signs

Introduction

India has around 25% high-risk pregnant mothers, which leads to about 75% perinatal morbidities (Jaydeep et al,2017). The early prediction of a high-risk pregnancy and planning interventions can help in preventing complications and result in good pregnancy outcomes.

Complications arising from pregnancy and childbirth stand as the primary causes of mortality among women of reproductive age in both India and worldwide (Balsarkar, 2023). According to data from the World Health Organization, difficulties during pregnancy and childbirth claim the lives of over 830 women every day (Majella et al. 2019).

A high-risk pregnancy is broadly defined as one in which the mother, foetus, or both are at risk for morbidity or mortality before or after delivery. Danger signs of pregnancy are warning signs that women encounter during pregnancy, child birth and post-partum period. It is important, to know these warning signs for women and health care providers to rule out serious complications and initiate treatment immediately (Amrita et al 2020).

The most common danger signs during pregnancy those can increase the risk of maternal deaths are: vaginal bleeding, convulsions or fits, high fever, abdominal pain, severe headache, blurred vision, absence of foetal movements, gush of fluid from vagina, foul smelling vaginal discharge etc. Maternal morbidity and mortality can be reduced significantly if women and their families can recognize the danger signs on time and seek proper health care (Kabakyenga et al. 2011). Delay in seeking health care is one of the key factors leading to maternal deaths, which can be associated with lack of awareness about obstetric danger signs. So, it is essential that pregnant women should be aware about danger signs of obstetric complications so that they can seek timely health care. (Felix et al 2018).

The danger signs are not the actual obstetric complications, but symptoms those are easily identified by non-clinical personnel. The commonest danger signs during pregnancy and labor include severe vaginal bleeding, swollen hands/face, blurred vision, prolonged labor, convulsions, retained placenta, fever, decreased fetal movements and sudden gush of amniotic fluid. (Dereje et al 2017). Lack of awareness about these danger signs is one of the reasons for failure of women to identify and seek appropriate emergency care (UNFPA,2004). Therefore, by considering above facts, it is felt necessary to study awareness of pregnancy -related risks among rural pregnant women.

Methodology

Total 150 rural women who are pregnant during the time of the study residing in 5 villages of Parbhani district namely Daithna, Nandapur,

Pandhri, Takali and Zari of Marathwada region, Maharashtra State were selected to conduct this research study as the investigator was having easy approach to them. After obtaining consent from the rural pregnant women, the data pertaining to the study were collected by personally interviewing them based on structured and open-ended interview schedule. Besides it, Kuppuswamy's socio-economic status (SES) scale revised by Dr. Sheikh Mohd. Saleem (2018) was administered on them for assessing their SES. Data collected from the rural pregnant women were pooled, tabulated, statistically analysed and discussed.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 and Fig 1.1 illustrates about awareness of rural pregnant women about the common symptoms of pregnancy. All the middle SES rural pregnant women reported that, nausea is a common symptom of pregnancy which was followed by amenorrhea (65.00%), craving for specific food items (63.33%), loss of appetite (35.00%), breast tenderness (28.33%). The corresponding percentages of their counterpart's low SES rural pregnant women, were observed to be 93.33, 85.55, 50.00, 26.66,12.22.

Based on SES, statistically significant differences were recorded regarding the awareness of rural pregnant women about the common symptoms of pregnancy. As awareness of symptoms of pregnancy helps women to identify complications at an early stage and to reduce the health risks, these findings indicate that there is a great need to raise awareness about these symptoms among rural women.

Table 2 and Fig 1.2 indicates about awareness of rural pregnant women about high risk pregnancy. About 80-91 percent rural pregnant women stated that pregnant women having low Hb level, heart diseases, diabetes mellitus and tuberculosis are considered as high risk pregnancy. Whereas a higher percentage of middle SES rural pregnant women (8.00%) expressed that women having weight below 45kg, short stature and are primigravida or grand multipara (41.66%) are the conditions of high-risk pregnancy. The corresponding percentages of their counter parts low SES rural pregnant women were noticed to be 47.77, 38.88 and 11.11.

Statistically no significant differences were recorded among low and middle SES rural pregnant women about their awareness regarding common symptoms of high-risk pregnancy.

Table 3 and Fig 1.3 illustrates awareness of rural pregnant women about bad obstetric history. Bad obstetric history (BOH) implies unfavourable fetal outcome. About 66-91 percent of the middle SES rural pregnant women expressed that low birth weight babies (66.66%), still birth, intrauterine growth retardation (75.00% each) and caesarean section are some of the conditions which indicate bad

obstetric history. The corresponding percentages of their counterparts low SES rural pregnant women were observed to be 45.55, 35.50, 65.55 and 91.11. Whereas 46.66 percent middle SES and 13.33 percent low SES rural pregnant women stated that repeated abortions are considered as bad obstetric history. On the other hand, irrespective of SES as very few of the rural pregnant women (8-13%) were found to be aware about causes of bad obstetric history such as breech delivery, fetal distress (8.00% each), prolonged rupture of membrane (11.66%), early onset of labour (10.66%), congenital anomalies and antepartum haemorrhage (12.66%).

Statistical results indicate that significantly a higher percentage of middle SES rural pregnant women were aware about some conditions like low-birth-weight babies, intrauterine growth retardation and pre-term delivery as bad obstetric history than their counterparts low SES rural pregnant women. These results specify that it is essential to sensitize rural families about general pregnancy issues considered as bad obstetric history for avoiding complications those may occur before and after the delivery of women.

Awareness of rural pregnant women about the danger signs of pregnancy are depicted in the Table 4 and Fig 1.4. About 58-95 percent of the middle SES rural pregnant women expressed that severe headache (58.33%), abdominal pain (60.00%), convulsions (71.66%), excessive vomiting, persistent swelling specially on legs (76.66%), lack of fetal movement (80.00%) and vaginal bleeding (95.00%) are some of the dangerous signs during pregnancy.

Overall, as compared to the middle SES rural pregnant women were observed to be knowing about above mentioned dangerous signs of pregnancy. In addition to these signs about 10-31 percent of low and middle SES rural pregnant women stated that visual disturbances and

difficult breathing are the danger signs of pregnancy and such women immediately need to get medical services for saving pregnant women's and newborn's life.

Statistical results proved that as compared to the low SES rural pregnant women significantly a higher percentage of middle SES rural pregnant women were aware about dangerous signs during pregnancy. The findings are in support of some of the results observed by Oni et al. (2016), Haleema et al. (2019) and Shamanewadi et al. (2020).

Conclusion

Irrespective of Socio- economic status, it was observed that a higher percentage of rural pregnant women (87-92 %) were unaware about bad obstetric history like congenital anomalies, early onset of labour, prolonged rupture of membrane, preterm delivery, breech delivery and fetal distress. With respect to the awareness of rural pregnant women about danger signs of pregnancy, even though a higher percentage of them (60-89 %) were aware about some signs like vaginal bleeding/ discharge, weak fetal movements, convulsions and persistent swelling are dangerous in pregnancy, however majority of them (43-87%) were found to be unaware about signs like excessive vomiting, severe headache, visual disturbances, difficulty in breathing and abdominal pain are hazardous signs during this period. On the whole, these results indicate that there is a great need to educate pregnant women about obstetric danger signs, which could go a long way in improving the maternal and fetal outcomes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the rural pregnant women for providing required data to carry out this research work. The authors also acknowledge concerned authorities of VNMKV, Parbhani for providing essential facilities to conduct this research study.

Table 1: Awareness of rural pregnant women about the common symptoms of pregnancy

Awareness of pregnant women about the common symptoms of pregnancy	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status(n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Nausea	93.33(84)	100(60)	96.00(144)	02.60**
Amenorrhoea	85.55(77)	65.00(39)	77.33(116)	02.77**
Craving for specific food items	50.00(45)	63.33(38)	55.33(83)	01.59 ^{NS}
Loss of appetite	26.66(24)	35.00(21)	30.00(45)	01.16 ^{NS}
Breast tenderness	12.22(11)	28.33(17)	18.66(28)	02.37*

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies of rural pregnant women

*P < 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level NS- Non Significant

Fig.1.1: Awareness of the pregnant women about the common symptoms of pregnancy

Table 2: Awareness of rural pregnant women about high risk pregnancy

Awareness about high-risk pregnancy	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status (n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Low Hb level	80.00(72)	88.33(53)	83.33(125)	01.34 ^{NS}
Weight below 45 kg	47.77(43)	81.66(49)	61.33(92)	00.24 ^{NS}
Primigravida or grand multipara	38.88(35)	41.66(25)	40.00(60)	01.76 ^{NS}
Short stature	11.11(13)	16.66(10)	15..33(23)	00.55 ^{NS}
Pregnant women having				

Heart diseases	86.66(78)	90.00(54)	88.00(132)	00.75 ^{NS}
Diabetes mellitus	85.55(77)	91.66(55)	88.00(132)	01.13 ^{NS}
Tuberculosis	83.33(75)	91.66(55)	86.66(130)	01.47 ^{NS}
Vaginal bleeding	86.66(78)	88.33(53)	87.33 (131)	01.76 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies, NS- Non-Significant

Fig.1.2: Awareness of rural pregnant women about high risk pregnancy

Table 3: Awareness of rural pregnant women about bad obstetric history

Awareness about bad obstetric history	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status (n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Caesarean section	91.11(82)	91.66(55)	91.33(137)	---
Still birth	65.55(59)	75.00(45)	69.33(104)	01.33 ^{NS}
Low birth weight babies	45.55(41)	66.66(40)	54.00(81)	02.60 ^{**}
Repeated abortions	43.33(30)	46.66(28)	38.66(58)	00.36 ^{NS}
Intrauterine growth retardation	35.50(32)	75.00(45)	51.33(77)	05.37 ^{**}
Antepartum haemorrhage	11.11(10)	15.00(09)	12.66(19)	00.70 ^{NS}
Congenital anomalies	08.88(08)	16.60(10)	12.00(18)	01.44 ^{NS}
Early onset of labour	08.88(08)	13.33(08)	10.66(16)	00.96 ^{NS}
Prolonged rupture of membrane	07.77(07)	11.66(07)	09.33(14)	00.82 ^{NS}
Preterm delivery	07.77(07)	21.66(13)	13.33(20)	02.37 [*]
Breech delivery	07.77(07)	08.33(05)	08.00(12)	0.22 ^{NS}
Fetal distress	04.44(04)	13.33(08)	08.00(12)	01.87 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies
 *P < 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level NS- Non Significant

Fig.1.3: Awareness of rural pregnant women about bad obstetric history

Table 4: Awareness of rural pregnant women about danger signs of pregnancy

Awareness about the danger sign of pregnancy	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status (n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Vaginal bleeding/ discharge	85.55(77)	95.00(57)	89.33(134)	02.12*
No/weak fetal movements	78.88(71)	80.00(48)	79.33(119)	00.29 ^{NS}
Convulsions	60.00(54)	71.66(43)	64.66(97)	01.40 ^{NS}
Abdominal pain	55.55(50)	60.00(36)	57.33(86)	00.60 ^{NS}
Persistent swelling	53.33(48)	76.66(46)	62.66(94)	03.01**
Excessive vomiting	44.44(40)	73.33(44)	56.00(84)	03.73**
Severe headache	27.77(25)	58.33(35)	40.00(60)	03.92**
Visual disturbances	18.88(17)	31.66(19)	24.00(36)	01.80 ^{NS}
Difficulty in breathing	10.00(9)	18.33(11)	13.33(20)	01.36 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies

*P < 0.05 level

**P < 0.01 level

NS- Non Significant

Fig.1. 4: Awareness of rural pregnant women about danger signs of pregnancy

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